

THE ROLE OF THE TASK "ABOUT MIXTURES" FOR MODERN FOOD PRODUCERS AND THE IMPROVEMENT OF INFANT FORMULA

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Annotation: The need for formation of professional competence «biotechnology and cave safety» was founded in the work, by acquiring skills in various biotechnological situations, in algorithm, long-know tasks «about mixtures», in about «diet». It is known that these tasks were not widely used on the track due to the complexity of the calculations, which today is not an obstacle in conditions modern advances in IT-technologies.

Key words: biotechnology and cave safety, the work, about mixtures, calculations, conditions, that these tasks, about «diet»

INTRODUCTION

Depending on the object of research and the formulation of the problem, the structure and content of the mathematical model of this problem have different forms. For example, our undergraduates developed mathematical models in their scientific activities and solved problems about mixtures in various forms. At the Kazakh National Agrarian University, many undergraduates majoring in IT technologies are engaged in research on this problem. Such activities are more beneficial for the formation of professional competencies of the specialty biotechnology and food safety. With the involvement of undergraduates of this specialty, we carried out research and solved a very interesting task, the so-called: "Using a diet model to create a baby food product, ideally close to mother's milk in composition."

A natural food product, milk, is valued for the content in its composition of a large amount of nutrients - vitamins, enzymes, fats, amino acids. It is the main supplier of calcium to the body, which both children and adults cannot do without, and lactose feeds the human brain [1-14].

Numerous studies confirming the indisputable biological advantage and the fundamental indispensability of natural feeding for the optimal development of the child have served as a basis for considering female milk as a universal model for creating infant formula [2-5].

METHOD AND RESULTS

In our work, we consider obtaining such a mixture, which in composition will be close to mother's milk. Sheep's, goat's, cow's and mare's milk are mixed. To do this, we use data on the biological composition of the products in question and apply a slightly modified mathematical model "The Problem of mixtures".

The aim of the work is to obtain a mixture containing various nutritional values, vitamins, macro- and microelements in sufficient quantities for all the types of nutrition elements under consideration, namely similar to mother's milk. The price is also taken into account by minimizing the costs of different types of products used (milk). To solve this problem, the theoretical basis of the diet problem was used. The problem was solved with the "Solution Search" package in the MS Excel environment. As a result, an optimal solution was obtained, which can be interpreted as follows: by mixing mare's milk $x_1 = 0.240$ liters or 239.89 ml; cow's milk $x_2 = 0.295$ l or 294.74 ml; goat's milk $x_3 = 0.114$ l or 114.62 ml and sheep's milk $x_4 = 0.351$ l or 350.75 ml. we get a mixture that is not inferior and even surpasses the presence of maternal milk nutrition elements (more than 21 elements).

Conclusion. The calculations carried out can contribute to the creation of infant formula at a relatively affordable price and ideal in terms of the composition of nutrition elements, since it is obtained from natural products that are of great value for children's health. The mixture can be manufactured in biological laboratories, without large expenditures of money. Similarly, it is possible to obtain numerical solutions for the optimal composition of all types of nutritional value, vitamins, macro- and microelements of nutrition, taking into account changes in the composition of milk depending on the season of the year, the results of which can be useful for food safety specialists, scientists and biotechnologists of the relevant food industry.

CONCLUSION

Currently, the proposed methodology for the development of infant formula has been transferred to the "Plant of the Kazakh Academy of Nutrition Amiran" LLP, Almaty, where a post-registration clinical trial of infant formula developed according to this technique has begun. To date, this plant has been and remains the first and only one in Kazakhstan for the production of infant formula made from natural whole milk of the highest quality.

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